

PARTICULARS OF THE ETHICS OF MEDICAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to present some particularities of the ethics of medical communication. Today the communication process is an integral part of the activity of an individual or a community. Due to the events of recent years, marked by the COVID-19 pandemic, communication in the medical sector has become vital, for the community but also for the individual. Advances in health have increased remarkably. New knowledge about managing disease as well as life-threatening problems has led to the development of better health management. Ethics must be at the heart of health communication. Ethical principles must be incorporated into all health communication activities. Only ethical communication will eliminate the risks of medical errors and the financial consequences and loss of the image of the medical institution. Ethical medical communication will influence people's health-related beliefs and/or behaviors. It will influence people's orientation towards medical information regarding certain health risks. It will influence people to adopt healthy lifestyles. It will influence the choice of healthy behaviors to maintain a quality of life at the highest qualitative level. Health communication activities raise a multitude of ethical concerns. Ethical concern is particularly directed at personal preferences and deep-rooted social values.

Keywords: Ethics of medical communication, ethical principles of medical communication, medical act, ethical communication as an integral part of the medical process, quality of life

1. Introduction

The problem of communication is an important problem of modern society today. Communication affects directly or indirectly, for an indefinite period, the lives of people but also of communities and the whole society. Communication as a specifically human characteristic can be considered as a binder for individuals in a community.

Communication offers the possibility of knowing people's opinions. It offers the possibility of psychosocial homogenization, which ensures a normal functioning of the community, regardless of its size.

Communication is a complex phenomenon. All definitions of human communication have common elements. Thus, communication is the process of transmitting information, ideas, opinions, different meanings from one community to another, from individual to individual. The communication process today is an integral part of the activity of the individual or the community.

Due to the events of recent years, marked by the COVID-19 pandemic, communication in the medical sector has become vital, for the community but also for the individual. Advances in health have increased remarkably. New knowledge about managing disease as well as life-threatening problems has led to the development of better health management. Diseases are better controlled. The right framework has been created for achieving extended longevity, especially for patients with disabilities and for patients with chronic diseases. The conditions were created to change the demographic characteristics as well as the epidemiological characteristics of communities and society.

The evolution of health systems today allows better management of patients with chronic diseases/with multiple morbidity. Their treatment requires the presence of health professionals.

The development of medical knowledge has allowed the introduction of more specialty and subspecialty fields in medical practice. Today healthcare services are grouped around areas of medical practice. The trend of specialization leads to a fragmentation of medical organizations. Thus health systems have migrated from acute to chronic care practices, from centralized care practices to decentralized care practices. Now medical professionals focus especially on their specialty area. They accumulate knowledge and specialist terms specific to their medical field. Accumulation of multiple new information as well as specialization make medical professionals to find a way of communication conducive and ethical for integrated patient care.

To provide effective and quality care, medical professionals need effective communication. Unfortunately, medical organizations today suffer from a series of communication deficiencies. Communication deficits constitute a vulnerability of the medical system. For patient safety, the risk of errors and communication failures must be eliminated. Recent studies have shown that errors as well as communication failures in medical organizations lead to enormous inefficiencies in health systems. They waste precious time and resources for the healthcare system.

2. Results and discussions

An essential component in medical communication is managerial communication. Managerial communication presents several particularities determined by the complexity of communication, the goals and objectives of communication as well as its implications. In medical organizations, these particularities must comply with the norms imposed by the managerial culture and/or company policy.

The specialized literature on the issue of managerial communication identifies new relevant characteristics of managerial communication: process based on feedback, the use of permanent or scheduled informational activities, etc. The characteristics of managerial communication are determined by the performance of communication functions.

Managerial communication must be done in a timely and permanent manner. This can be done vertically upwards (up from the base), downwards (from top to bottom towards the base), horizontally (between employees in the same department/direction/office, on the same hierarchical level). It can be done through formal communication channels (pre-established channels) or through informal channels when information is conveyed without direct and/or immediate utility. Informal communication channels are spontaneous; they are constantly changing. They operate at all levels in an organization. Voinea (2015) showed that a formal internal communication is based on the operation of the communication system according to the communication rules and procedures established by internal norms at the organization level.

Two types of communication networks are mentioned in the specialized literature: centralized networks where information is transmitted to the central point and decentralized networks specific to complex activities (Cerban, 2012).

In the process of transmitting the message, an information flow can pass through several hierarchical levels to reach the recipient. We are talking about linear communication. It can be horizontal, vertical, ascending or descending. All these types of communication are based on a hierarchical route of formal communication stability through internal norms of the organization.

In every company/organization, internal managerial communication is dependent on the organizational climate. In practice, two types of organizational climate are usually encountered: defensive climate and closed climate. Internal managerial communication in an organization is dependent on factors such as the organizational structure, communication barriers, the rules of formal communication, the impact of informal communication, the communication climate dependent on the subordinate relationships in the organization.

In the medical organization, there is an internal communication as well as an external communication between the representatives of the organization and the external environment. If internal communication is vital in carrying out the medical act, external communication is essential for patient satisfaction, for maintaining the image of the medical organization. Internal and external communication are essential for fulfilling the purpose of the medical act.

Medical institutions possess ethical values that are respected by all its members. Every manager knows how to communicate inside and outside his institution for the protection of the image of the medical organization and his own image. The medical staff must permanently reconsider their attitude related to ethical principles, inside and outside the institution in mutual actions with the social environment.

Hospitals are the most important category of medical institutions. They often face at least two types of ethical problems. In hospitals there are problems related to the relationships established between doctor and patient during medical research activities. These relationships must be controlled by clear and well-defined rules and regulations. An instructive example is that of informed consent. In hospitals, there are problems related to internal and external relations with other institutions within or outside the medical system. Some external relations are regulated by specific internal procedures, others are not.

The main actors in a medical institution involved in ethical communication are presented below

Figure 1. The main actors in medical institutions involved in ethical communication

The main actors in each medical institution form three groups. They must work together through a communication based on ethical principles to perform the medical act.

In general, medical personnel consider all the values generated by the application of medical ethics to be predominant. Emphasis is placed on patients' right to be informed. Emphasis is placed on patients' right to decide whether they agree with the proposed therapy. The executive (administrative) staff is always guided by marketing principles aiming at the optimal and best development of their institution.

A lack of communication between these two important actors can generate real conflicts. To eliminate this vulnerability of the medical institution, ethical and effective communication is needed to offer patients a better quality of life.

Another extremely important category of relationships built inside a medical institution is communication with society. It is extremely important that how resources are used in the short and long term in providing necessary medical services can have ethical implications for the local community.

In carrying out the medical act, it is important to develop a correct and honest method of communication between medical institutions. This ensures the provision of specific services for the community. The risk of false competitions is eliminated.

A leader in a medical institution has the responsibility of ensuring a real collaboration between all employees of the institution. Only in this way can ethical values be utilized in medical practice. If they are not already put into practice, it is recommended to generate documents on the ethical principles that must guide medical and research activities. These documents on ethical principles are complemented by an ethical code that defines for each institution its own values and the ethical principles that guide their activity. At the national level, there is an ethical code for medical personnel. It applies in all medical institutions. In addition, if necessary, other ethical values and principles will be applied to ensure, at the level of each institution, an appropriate ethical framework for performing the medical act.

Ethical problems regarding communication arise not only within the institution, but also from outside it. An instructive example is that of the manager who must admit and decide whether

or not to publicize medical errors during an event. There is still a degree of reluctance to frankly admit "what went wrong". There are still fears that could be justified by possible legal and/or financial consequences.

In order to ensure an adequate quality of medical services in everyday practice, a permanent concern regarding compliance with ethical regulations is necessary. It constitutes an essential fact. It is correct and offers real support in the situation of being subjected to a great external and/or internal pressure, a consequence of social and economic conditions.

The trust that should be given to medical personnel must be encouraged. Medical personnel belonging to the health system must integrate the ethical principles of communication in their daily work. This will lead to evolution; it will lead to a better picture of patients.

Only through an ethical approach to communication will the rigid attitudes that still persist among some managers in medical institutions be eliminated. They will eliminate the rigid attitude regarding the medical errors that may inherently occur. When an event occurs in which medical errors occur, the medical staff must adopt an ethical attitude. He must tell the truth regardless of the consequences.

Those who are against an open recognition of their own errors rely on the fact that patients can sue only if they are aware of the medical errors produced. Many times it is considered that admitting errors only increases the risk of legal actions taken against the institution. The latest statistics show that for errors of minor or moderate consequence, most patients do not intend to take legal action if medical errors are recognized.

Honest acknowledgment of medical errors often allows for compensatory measures. Lately, there has been a change in the approach to patients in the case of medical errors. Based on the legal regulations in force related to malpractice patients take legal action more and more frequently. Many times the actions in the court are also determined by the revolt of the patients if the medical errors that have occurred are hidden by specialized personnel and discovered later by the patient.

If ethical communication is not used, there is the risk of huge financial losses but also the risk of losing the image of the medical institution. In the current economic and social context, the role of the manager but also of the entire medical staff becomes essential in approaching and applying ethical principles in communication.

Conclusions

Ethics must be at the heart of health communication. Ethical principles must be incorporated into all health communication activities. Only ethical communication will eliminate the risks of medical errors and the financial consequences and loss of the image of the medical institution. Ethical medical communication will influence people's health-related beliefs and/or behaviors. It will influence people's orientation towards medical information regarding certain health risks. It will influence people to adopt healthy lifestyles. It will influence the choice of healthy behaviors to maintain a quality of life at the highest qualitative level.

Health communication activities raise a multitude of ethical concerns. Ethical concern is particularly directed at personal preferences and deep-rooted social values.

The general intent of health communication interventions is to promote the health of individuals or communities. Communication aimed at influencing people's health involves ethical issues. Ethical health communication involves addressing critical issues for the individual and/or community, namely responsibility, risk, and social and cultural values.

In order to carry out a medical act to the required quality standards, in addition to other factors, ethical communication is necessary. Ethical communication increases the trust of individuals and communities in the image and in medical institutions. Many vulnerabilities and risks of medical institutions are eliminated by an ethical communication approach.

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